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ECOTOURISM POTENTIAL AND WAYS OF ITS USAGE IN THE MOUNTAINOUS AREAS OF AZERBAIJAN (THE CASE OF THE SHAKI-ZAGATALA ECONOMIC-GEOGRAPHICAL REGION)

Abstract. Tourism provides a basis for high income and quick return on investment. In a broader sense, tourism is a means affecting the formation of the state budget, the improvement of villages and cities, the preservation of historical and architectural monuments, and the development of small and medium enterprises. The mountainous areas of Azerbaijan are spectacular in terms of tourism, especially ecotourism. Because natural conditions and resources have a decisive impact on the formation and future development of ecotourism in these areas. This increases the strength of the socio-economic development of villages in mountainous areas and affects the importance of the relationship between tourism and the environment (ecotourism). However, in modern times, the level of use of natural tourism resources in Azerbaijan is inadequate. It is commonly known that the material and social needs of the rural population in mountainous areas are met mainly through local natural resources and opportunities. In modern times, the main occupation of the population in the mountainous areas of the world's leading countries is based on the use of ecotourism resources. Because of the conditions of structurally limited production, the difficulty of finding employment in mountainous areas aggravates the situation, combined with the activity of demographic processes (high natural increase) in places. To overcome these problems taking into account local opportunities such as climatic conditions, landscapes, forest resources, mineral and thermal water of medical importance, etc. is one of the priority directions of ecotourism development.

Keywords: natural tourism resources, tourism, ecotourism, mountain rural settlements, socio-economic development

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ПОТЕНЦИАЛ ЭКОТУРИЗМА И ПУТИ ЕГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ В ГОРНЫХ РАЙОНАХ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ШЕКИ-ЗАГАТАЛЬСКОГО ЭКОНОМИКО-ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКОГО РАЙОНА)

Туристическая сфера обеспечивает основу для высоких доходов и быстрой окупаемости инвестиций. В более широком смысле туризм – это средство, влияющее на формирование государственного бюджета, благоустройство сельских и городских населённых пунктов, сохранение памятников истории и архитектуры, развитие малого и среднего предпринимательства. Горные районы Азербайджана очень аттрактивны с точки зрения туризма, особенно экотуризма. Здесь природные условия и ресурсы оказывают решающее влияние на становление и дальнейшее развитие экотуризма. Они способствуют социально-экономическому развитию горных сел и связана между туризмом (экотуризм) и окружающей средой. Однако в настоящее время уровень использования природных ресурсов в целях развития туризма в Азербайджане недостаточен. Общеизвестно, что материальные и социальные потребности сельского населения в горных районах удовлетворяются в основном за счёт местных природных ресурсов и возможностей. В современное время основное занятие населения горных районов в ведущих странах мира основано на использовании потенциала экотуризма. Сложные орографические условия затрудняют развитие промышленно-производственных сфер хозяйства, что сказывается на возможностях трудоустройства местного населения. Также, как правило, в таких регионах наблюдается активность демографических процессов (высокий естественный прирост). Преодоление этих проблем с учётом местных возможностей, таких как климатические условия, ландшафты, лесные ресурсы, минеральные и термальные воды лечебного значения и др., является одним из приоритетных направлений развития экотуризма.

Ключевые слова: *природные туристские ресурсы, туризм, экотуризм, горные сельские поселения, социально-экономическое развитие.*

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Introduction

In current conditions, it is substantial to determine the economic development potential of countries and regions, and the consistent and coherent implementation of the system of measures they envisage. Thus, there is a demand to diversify the economic structure of the country, which has great natural and human potential, namely the formation of complex state-of-the-art economic sectors and regions. In this respect, tourism is factored in as one of the best methods to meet this need.

Any country rich in natural resources can increase the competitiveness of the national tourism complex by integrating it into the international tourism market. Since the development strategy of tourism is measured, first of all, by natural-tourism resources, then by the demand for tourism products and the level of services provided to tourists.

For the purpose of improving tourism, which is taken into consideration the most promising area of the non-oil sector in Azerbaijan, the "Law on Tourism" was adopted in 1999, and the "State Programs on the Development of Tourism in the Republic of Azerbaijan" in 2002-2005 and 2010-2014, "State Program on the Development of Resorts in the Republic of Azerbaijan" in 2009-2018. Moreover, declaring the year 2011 as "the year of Tourism", the Strategic Roadmap for the Development of the Specialized Tourism Industry in the Republic of Azerbaijan" in 2016 and other decrees were of great importance in the development of tourism. However, despite affairs implemented, it has not been feasible to fully and comprehensively discuss the existing challenges in the tourism sector.

In order to develop the tourism sector of Azerbaijan on a global scale, relevant laws have been adopted, and the implementation of state programs and strategic roadmaps has begun. In a short period of time, a favourable environment for the development of tourism has been created, a national tourism quality system has been established to increase tourist satisfaction, and tourism centres have been developed and pro-

moted. Nevertheless, these measures are primarily implemented in the capital Baku and other major cities. In this circumstance, the rural settlements located in the mountainous areas of the country are far from these projects. This situation, in turn, reflects itself in the socio-economic advancement of villages.

According to a number of experts, at the present time, tourism is becoming more "green", special attention has been paid to the environmental friendliness of resorts and destinations, aspects of tourism, and the number of tourists is gradually growing. Preservation of natural complexes, and natural, relatively untouched economic activities are chosen as potential areas for more vacationers [1]. Without a doubt that this is possible with the development of ecotourism in the regions. Because the development of ecotourism, in addition to determining the socio-economic potential of the regions, is closely involved in the employment of the local population. This area also assists to bring into the open the differences within the region, and its development provides full and effective use of the potential of a number of infrastructure areas.

Material and methods

The laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan, decrees and orders signed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, adopted "State Programs", statistical collections published by the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the fund materials of the Institute of Geography named after acad. H.A.Aliyev (ANAS), scientific works and methodical instructions of scientists conducting research in this field comprise of the theoretical and practical basis of the research.

The research was carried out using historical and comparative analysis, a systematic approach, statistical-mathematical and other methods.

Ecotourism

As a trend, the term ecotourism emerged in the 1870s and 1880s and it indicated itself as a balanced local idea carrier to gain economic profit and achieve ecological security using natu-

ral recreational resources efficiently for the purpose of protecting nature based on the idea that the Earth is the source of life [14, p. 105]. The goals and objectives of ecotourism are the efficient use of nature to ensure ecological security and sustainable development for present and future generations [5]. Ecotourism is a type of tourism in which its nature is less altered by humans and serves to improve the environment. In other words, it is a form of environmental protection. An ecotourist obtains information about the environment, comes in contact with nature and evaluates it. The fundamental factor reflecting the attractive and sustainable socio-economic nature of ecotourism is national parks.

According to the International Ecotourism Organization, "ecological tourism (eco-tourism) is a responsible journey to natural areas, areas that protect the environment and support the well-being of local people" [13].

Being a special form of nature tourism, ecotourism is tourism related to the care of the environment. Specialized trips are usually organized in small groups. During such trips, guides endeavour to enucleate to tourists the importance of loving nature, protecting natural resources and preserving the environment [15, p. 44].

Ecotourism is a sustainable type of tourism that has the specific potential to meet the needs of the environment and the well-being of the local population. This type of tourism has directed the protection of nature, improving the economic and social life of the local population, obtaining intriguing information about the region, and the formation of ecological culture through the organization of ecological tours and other matters. Generally speaking, the essential purpose of ecotourism can be compartmentalised as follows [7, p. 75]:

- preserving and studying biodiversity;
- rest in the bosom of nature;
- organization of ecological and cultural tours;
- formation of ecological culture;
- ensuring socio-economic stability.

Analyse

Azerbaijan is considered one of the most attractive countries in the world in terms of tourism. Natural richness, diversity of cultural and historical monuments, ethnic diversity, being a country of multiculturalism and other advantages have laid the foundation for the development of tourism in the country. Especially, Baku, Ganja, Nakhchivan, Naftalan and other large cities are the essential tourist destination centres where tourists are more concentrated. Notwithstanding, the mountainous areas lag far behind in this regard.

In order to expand the participation of mountainous areas of Azerbaijan in the tourism sector, it is necessary to improve the tourism infrastructure from a regional point of view. Because the tourism infrastructure acts as a guarantor of development, provides inter-regional multifaceted communication, as well as intra-regional communications [2].

According to the calculations of the geographers, although 78% of the Republic of Azerbaijan is convenient for settlement, this indicator for the mountainous areas is lower one and half times than that standing at 52,9% [17, p. 208]. This situation, in turn, manifests itself both in the settlement area and in the establishment of a tourism economy.

According to statistical data in the year 2019, 2,4% of the volume of the GDP in Azerbaijan was accounted for by the tourism industry [4, p. 101]. This figure was just 1,0% in 2010. The reason for the increase was the announcement of 2011 as the "Year of Tourism". In the same year, \$ 828 million was invested in the tourism industry, as a result of which the tourism industry began to develop rapidly, new hotels were built in a short time, and the number of tourists visiting the country increased 2,5 times.

The improvement of tourism is not just limited to being a high-income sector. This area is important in discussing social challenges, reducing and annihilating unemployment, increasing the economic and social development of the regions, as well as improving the living standards of

the population. Being a labour-intensive sector, tourism is a powerful tool in preventing migration in the regions, especially in remote mountain villages, as well as opening up opportunities for the development of small and medium enterprises [8, p. 156].

One of the primary conditions for increasing revenues from tourism services is to attract both domestic and foreign investment in this area. Since investment has a positive impact on the development of the tourism sector, as well as the life and economic activities of the local population. However, the role of tourism resources in the socio-economic development of the population living in mountainous areas is underestimated. To overcome this problem, the use of ecotourism potential in mountainous areas is given priority. Importantly, it should not be forgotten that ecotourism cannot be organized anywhere. Because there must be necessary conditions for the development of ecological routes on a scientific basis and the organization of ecotours.

Of the 11 climate types that exist in the world, 9 exist in Azerbaijan. This factor, undoubtedly, plays a pivotal role in the formation of rich biodiversity in our country. There are about 4500 plant species in Azerbaijan, which constitute 64% of the rich flora of the Caucasus. Of these, 240 are endemic and relict species. The Red Book of the Republic of Azerbaijan includes 140 rare and endangered plant species. The species of fauna distributed here: 14000 insects, 123 fish, 9 aquatic creatures, 54 reptiles, 360 birds and 99 mammals, 108 of which are listed in the Red Book [3, p. 8].

The revival of tourism is primarily observed in the summer season. During the summer months, tourists travel to various places for recreation, preferring to relax in an environmentally friendly environment. In such conditions, small mountain villages located in mountainous areas are of special interest to tourists. This creates a basis for the development of ecotourism, as well as improving the socio-economic situation in rural areas.

One of the regions of Azerbaijan developed

in recent years in terms of ecotourism is the Shaki-Zagatala economic-geographical region, located in the north-western part of the country, on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus Mountains.

Having 8,84 thousand km² in total area, the Shaki-Zagatala economic-geographical region forms 10,2% of the territory of the country and 6,2% of the total population (630,4 thousand people, 2020). The population density is 71 people per km² [12, p. 660]. The settlement system of the economic-geographical region is represented by 6 administrative districts, 6 cities, 8 small towns and 336 rural settlements.

The investigated area is distinguished by its unique *natural conditions* and *relief* features. Being subjected to the fragmentation at a small distance (20-30 km.), the area is divided into three important areas according to its natural conditions: the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus, the Ganikh-Ayrichay valley, the Middle Kura foothills (Ajinohur and Turud-Sarija plains and mountainous part of Shaki). The area is generally located at an altitude of 100 m to 4466 m above sea level. It is mainly represented by highlands such as mountain-steppe, mountain-forest, subalpine and alpine meadows and nival area [11, p. 35-36]. Natural conditions and relief features have great potential for the development of ecotourism in the area. These opportunities mainly cover the mountainous areas of the economic-geographical region.

One of the most important features of ecotourism is its dependence on climate [10]. The climatic features of the Shaki-Zagatala economic-geographical region are primarily mild-humid. The area receives abundant solar energy throughout the year. The number of sunny hours fluctuates between 2200-2300 per year and the total solar radiation is 120-148 kcal / cm². The average annual temperature fluctuates between 6-14°C in the Balakan district and 0-14°C in other districts. The amount of annual precipitation is 300-350 mm. around Acinohur, 500-700 mm. in Ganikh-Ayrichay, and 900-1300 mm. in mountainous areas [6]. Such favourable climatic condi-

tions create bening conditions for the development of ecotourism in the area. This condition can be felt mainly in the summer months.

It is an undeniable fact that **forests** are considered attractive areas for tourism, and there is great potential for the development of ecotourism in these areas. The Shaki-Zagatala economic-geographical region has rich forest resources. The forests contain valuable species of trees such as oak, hornbeam, elm, and pine, which also make up 27% of the total area [16, p. 221].

The use of **water resources** for the purpose of ecotourism is one of the necessary factors. In

this respect, the Shaki-Zagatala economic-geographical region is one of the regions of Azerbaijan with rich water resources. Depending on the structural and lithological features of the rock layers they pass through, numerous waterfalls have formed in the valleys of mountain rivers [9]. There are large river systems such as Damiraparan, Kish, Gurmuk, Shin, Mazim, Katekh, Mukhakh, and Balakanchay in the territory of the economic-geographical region. These rivers can be used to organise ecotourism activities. Thus, Ilisu, Khalkhal, Shirshir, Katekh, Gabzidere and other waterfalls on the rivers engage tourists' attention.

Ilisu waterfall

Khalkhal waterfall

Gabzidere waterfall

Fig. 1 – Waterfalls are an attractive natural monument for the development of ecotourism

Ecotourism is directly related to the mechanisms and principles of using nature as a field of human activity. Because the resources involved in this form of tourism have an interaction with the natural environment [1]. In order to sustainably develop ecotourism in the Shaki-Zagatala economic-geographical region, firstly, it is necessary to understand its essence and conduct a structural analysis, which means accepting the use of natural resources as an ecotourism environment. During ecotourism trips, issues such as minimising damage to the environment, increasing the value of environmental education, studying natural landscapes and protecting biodiversi-

ty, the sum and the substance of it, and nature protection are addressed.

For the moment, it is fairly difficult to assess the current state of development of ecotourism in the Shaki-Zagatala economic-geographical region. Although there are a few kinds of research in this area, statistics on international and local ecotourists are not available. For this reason, problems related to the development of ecotourism should be identified and ways to solve them should be explored.

Results

Mountainous areas are considered to be one of the areas that attract tourists with their

natural richness. There are great potential opportunities for the development of ecological, adventure, and extraordinary tourism. It can also play a substantial role in providing business opportunities for the local population. In order to develop the ecotourism sector in the Shaki-Zagatala economic-geographical region having ecotourism potential in Azerbaijan, the "Concept of the development of ecotourism " should be developed and this concept should include the

development of scientific and theoretical bases of ecotourism, inculcation of ways to raise ecological culture, training of ecotourism specialists, creation and assessment of cadastre of ecotourism objects, monitoring and forecasting, creation of ecotourism incentives and other essential issues. All these are likely to lay the foundation for the rapid development of ecotourism not only in the region we are studying but also in Azerbaijan.

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